

SHAPING HEALTH IN THE PUPILS OF THE SENIOR AND PREPARATORY GROUP OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

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Annotation. It is necessary to strengthen the focus on physical education and sports if we define the formation of a healthy lifestyle, health and health improvement as a forward task. Effective carrying out of the elements of shaping a healthy lifestyle is essential to start with MTTs.

Keywords: quality of health, healthy, nurturing, preservation, physical, mental, medical, flatulence.

The complex of actions in preschool educational organizations is 30% in fact the norm is 50%, in 6-8-year-olds 50% in 9-12-year-olds 60% in the upper classes 80% lack of action FAA, which in turn is the main factor for the appearance of a number of diseases. Therefore, it is recommended to adhere to a healthy lifestyle and regularly engage in physical education and sports. Obviously today, the need to engage in regular physical education among the population is very important, therefore, the need for formation, storage and strengthening will be the foundation. That is, it is necessary to strengthen the focus on physical education and sports if we define the formation of a healthy lifestyle, health and health improvement as a forward task. In order to effectively carry out the elements of shaping a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to build on 4 basic principles of health: spiritual, physical, mental, medical aspects. Such an approach forms health with a clear goal and also improves the vital activity of the body.

Further improvement of the issues of shaping a healthy lifestyle among the population consists in identifying an important object of popularization of sports and physical education among young people.

Experts from the World Health Organization have identified 4 factors affecting health quality and life expectancy in approximate proportions.

1. Hereditary factors -20%
2. Environmental impact-20%

3. Medical supply (health) - 10-15%
4. Human way of life-45-50%

Undoubtedly, it is fundamentally wrong to achieve health as a single tool, since not a single of the proposed approaches can cover all facets of the functional systems that make up the human body. It will not be easy to popularize and convey physical education and sports among young people so it will be advisable to use simple to complex, or achamiyally to fan and other tastes. For this:

1. Development of a plan of Health and physical activity programs for preschool children
2. Physical activity and nutrition
3. Positive attitude towards physical activity by dalvat aims to improve the overall level of physical activity
5. Using a multicomponent approach to stimulate physical activity
6. Engage young people to help identify appropriate provision and activities

Self-assessment and planning map provides a self-assessment program describes where it is now, and provides a plan address and directions are developed. A school health plan it is unlikely to be effective if it is systematically based on analysis of existing policies and practices, concepts derived from research and developed by a team that includes teachers, parents, school administrators, students and the community.

The overall analysis should not only be content analysis (available or non-existent) materials and initiatives, but also include the opinions of all stakeholders in the process of developing and implementing PE programs-students, teachers and other school staff. Assessment questionnaires can be developed for this. Analysis on evaluation criteria should point to accuracy, acceptability, feasibility and advantage of PE policies and applications.

The educational purpose of this stage is to program the school principals with simple steps to analyze the importance of school health assessment and the online resources of physical activity policies and programs to work to improve their physical activity during the school year, to plan, design physical activity initiatives. In Europe, the school physical education document provides information on national strategies, with large-scale initiatives to integrate sports in senior education, as well as training analysis and suggestions on how good PE is a built-in curriculum. The Universal survey of school physical education the document shows the findings on physical education curricula and programs

around the world, how to integrate sports in school curricula in a good way with suggestions.

Poor diet and chronic diseases, which account for 56.5%, are among the main risk factors million deaths each year and a global disease burden of 46%. It recognizes a major health problem, who has clear and convincing evidence that there is a high consumption of energy – sugar, starch and fat-a factor of chronic diseases associated with nutrition, which is of fundamental importance in relation to physical inactivity. A healthy diet and physical activity are key to a good diet and a long and healthy life that is necessary. Eating dense food and balancing energy consumption with the necessary physical activity is important at all stages of life to maintain health. High in energy and low in essential nutrients contributes to excess energy, heavy and obesity, consuming too much food. Globally simple, but very important, recommendations initiative are to eat less high-calorie food; especially food with high saturation or trans fat and sugar; eat food with unsaturated fat; use less salt; eat high amounts of fruits, vegetables and legumes; plant and sea choose foods origin; and be physically active for at least 30 minutes a day for study purpose.

The educational goal of this stage is how nutrition is related to physical activity and how adequate nutrition and stimulation of physical activity can become the cornerstone of a good health policy that can be school.

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